

Metacognitive Awareness and Quality of Work Life as Predictors of Professional Commitment

LynlynLanosOngcay, Lorna T. General
University of Mindanao Davao City Professional Schools

Abstract:- This study determined the metacognitive awareness, quality of work as predictor of professional commitment teachers in Caraga District. Quantitative non- experimental research utilizing the descriptive correlational research design in this study with a sample of 300 teachers. The researcher used sets of adapted survey questionnaires in obtaining data from the respondents which were subjected for content validity and reliability analysis. The data were analyzed using the Mean, Pearson- r, and Multiple Regression Analysis. The overall result revealed that the levels of metacognitive awareness, quality of work and professional commitment of teachers are evident most of the time. Moreover, metacognitive awareness and quality of work has significant influence on the professional commitment in Caraga District was proven in this study.

Keywords:- *Metacognitive awareness, quality of work, professional commitment, teachers.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In many organizations today, employees are dissatisfied with their tasks. The character of working history has combine of the administrative issues of modernization. "Quality of Work Life (QWL)" is a idea of human ability administration to improve whole history of employees. Quality of work existence is the characteristic of the connection between agents and the overall work atmosphere and involves human, technical and business-related concerns (Skalli,,Theodossiou, &Vasileiou, 2008).

A feature work life turns into a certain air of relationships and a well stimulated trained workers striving for progress. While fiscal benefits wait number one in conditions of cost, determinants such as material occupied environments, workplace rearrangement and design, course growth and advancement space are immediately acquire importance. Workers then wish administration to improve all these conveniences and through boost the quality of occupied history. A excellence of life admits staff members to focus on two together individual and group incident, that in turn leads to whole growth (Lane, Esser, Holte, & McCusker, (2010)).

Organizational engrossment maybe viewed as an enlargement of task vindication as it is the beneficial attitude staff members have towards the arranging alternatively their own work. However, with administrative obligation, feelings are much more forceful and are characterized by an worker's affection to the arrangement and willingness to create sacrifices for it (Martinez and others., 2009). Organizational date is a forerunner to job

delight (Gopinath, 2020).Boehman (2006) maintains that the intention of engagement is clear. Enthusiastic family like to push appendages of their institution toward the aims of the organization and set more exertion into their work. Because obligations have various purposes, other obligation writings frequently refer to administrative assurances or products of administrative commitments. Professional date is a form of work date trusted to influence performance and additional work effects.Going forward, the same dopes will explain reason scientists are concerned in determining professional date accompanying the friendship middle from two points metacognitive awareness and task characteristic, utilizing the indicators intentional, as no studies have happened administered still. is. Further research could supply few intuitiveness into how a meta-feature work existence take care of benefit savants. Similarly, academic institutions have plans about reason these developments occur and in what way or manner expert engrossment influences the connection between metacognitive idea and feature. of work existence.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

A. Professional Commitment

Professional Commitment Focusing on the link between scholar collegiality and lecturer professional obligation, many studies have designated that in schools where assistants agree to plan school bettering, select teaching orders and projects, and plan professor professional development and preparation, scholars likely expected more dedicated to their declaration. It is further supported that collegiality with education people helps bureaucracy to better evolve greater assurance levels (McCready &Soloway, 2010).Meanwhile, Teaching is not a "nine to five" type of job place you can just leave your work behind and pick it move backward in the dawn. It's a task that demands occasion and assurance. Dedicated teachers take their work home accompanying bureaucracy, not just concerning matter, but excitedly also. When their juniors are injuring, they are hurting. When entity isn't going right at school, therefore they are the one the one advocate for change. For a committed assistant, nothing is ever abandoned distraught. Teaching is a process, and they will continually be an alive subscriber to that process (Medland and others., 2010).Man is upwardly social person. For happy and serene growth he has to play miscellaneous acts. For better life instruction is a vital determinant for husband. Only skillful professor can best give instruction. But to act his/her burdens correctly, a instructor must be renewed professionally. Dedication to the declaration is of extreme significance. This dedication should by any means levels - lower to taller. The professor imparts instruction, transfer abilities and better attitudes of the graduates. The idea of

faithfulness and assurance is extremely main concerning the case of teachers' educators. Teacher educators are people as political whole the one train the potential Teachers the one educate the scholars, train the trainers (Farroq, 2012). Professional assurance increases flavor to teaching process. It must be part of routine and not a burden. Effective education is the capability, the knowledge of abilities, use of abilities lithely and creatively. Kohli et al., (2005) studied that coach's educator's professional obligation was a ignored extent in Punjab. It was argue moderate level. According to Agrawal & Goyal (2012) teacher educators was extreme in professional assurance concerning neuter, matrimonial rank and ability (Wang et al., 2009). In addition, For Karim and Rehman (2012) concerning feelings and intuition professional assurance is the labeling, sympathy, and connection of the member accompanying the employer. Usmani (2016) specified three elements of concerning feelings and intuition professional assurance-confidence and acknowledgment of arrangement's objectives enthusiasm to aim the aims and enthusiasm to assert enrollment of the organization). The second sign is duration professional assurance. rganization. Therefore, concerning feelings and intuition obligation is the only type of obligation wished expected inspired in an institution (Chan, & Wyatt, 2007). Continuance assurance wealth that the peasants cannot take the risk to leave their tasks as they accomplish the cost of giving up the space to a degree prosecute, retirement account rights and profit giving. The evidence that the laborers keep active at the arrangement as skilled are essentiality task opportunities and they will occurrence troubles in ceding their elementary abilities to another arranging forms continuance assurance. It refers to an knowledge of the costs guide leaving from and the benefits guide stopping in an arranging. Such workers link to and remain in an arranging cause they need commotion so (Conley & You, 2009). The tertiary rule is duration professional (CP). It is in a way bond between the laborer and the institution. It is established an exchange on correct contract. It is a type of contribution of the laborer accompanying organization (Ibrahim and others., 2015). It is the worker's need developing not enough monetary benefits, lack of options, preference rank and retreat benefits. It checks the agent to transfer welcome/her knowledge to additional organizations (Shoab, H., & Khalid, 2017). Continuance obligation method that the educators cannot take the risk to abandon their tasks as they accomplish the cost of giving in the opportunities in the way that do, retirement account rights and profit giving. The reality that the laborers hold working at the institution as skilled are essentiality task time and they will experience troubles in assigning their fundamental abilities to another arranging establishes duration commitment (Ugurlu, & Ozutku 2014). The second sign is normalizing professional assurance. It is the blame sense towards the institution. It is the moral base of individual concerning good or bad of the institution. People accompanying the extreme normalizing professional obligation resume active with the unchanging arrangement Swann (2010). It reflects a impression of responsibility in the second place recruitment. Such employees feel that they're operating at a loss and should wait accompanying an arrangement. It cultivates on the

support of a collection of pressures arise principles that things discover all the while their ancestral, enlightening and organizational socialization processes. Through preparing (rewards and penalties) and displaying (note and substitution of possible choice) crowd learn these principles (Delima, 2015).

B. Metacognitive Awareness

Metacognition is "the information of the character about his/her own intelligent processes and the habit concerning this information to control the cognitive processes" (Flavell, 1986). First studies on metacognition were told on account of the research administered by Flavell on the intelligence of the toddlers (Williams & Atkins, 2009). In the globe, that is changeful continuously and technologically, it is again troublesome to anticipate which facts will be unavoidable for the future. Besides it is absurd to obtain the vacant facts for all the things. Therefore, resolution reached for including the metacognition in the syllabus while cultivating the education curricula appears moderate. Gunstone and Northfield grown this view and submitted that teaching of metacognition must have a main significance in educator education (Yildiz & Akdag, 2017). The feature of instruction has happened absolutely changed apiece accelerated incident of science (Locatelli & Arroio, (2016). This condition (status of instruction) further concreted the way to change from coach-focused instruction to student-concentrated instruction, ending changing the unoriginal understanding of instruction (Kasim & Darus 2020). Furthermore, the critical parts of student-focused instruction are with the study procedures, place graduates use their metacognitive knowledge, regulating their own study processes, and seizing inspiration. Metacognitive knowledge, metacognitive experiences, metacognitive information, metacognitive assumptions, metacognitive abilities, high-level abilities, and above thought are few terms guide metacognition (Yesilyurt, 2013).

C. Quality of Work Life

Quality of work existence is a process by which interest groups in the institution will learn by means of what to work better together, by what method to decide for themselves what ventures, changes and improvements are attractive and productive to the institution expected more adept; as teachers at mechanics schools have various unification in the arrangement, work life and public reliance, overall temporary place to stay or sleep from the different theoretical schools, so, chief to various incident of human skill and growth freedom (Boas & Morin, 2019). Good work existence balance is most essential for each individual expected more efficient and persuasive with accomplish task vindication which in proper sequence guarantees achievement in welcome or her ventures. Work-life balance is essential to scholar influence and vindication in the circumstances of student knowledge. Researches have confirmed that a better work existence balance results in the wellness of the skill and again revised undergraduate demeanor. Moreover, good work growth balance gives a feel of task delight and likewise helps to achieve bigger memory rates in the organization (Punia, V., & Kamboj, 2013). Quality of Work existence improvements are outlined as some project that takes place at all level of an

organization that inquires better administrative effectiveness through the augmentation of human excellence and development. A process by which united states of america holders in the arranging, administration, unions and operators - discover how to agree better to decide for themselves what conduct, changes and betterings are seductive and workable so that reach the win and concurrent aims of an improved feature of growth working for all appendages of the arranging and greater influence for two together the guest and the unions (Mukherjee, 2010)The first rule of quality of work growth is work surroundings. Work atmosphere is a place at which point one everything. It is a friendly and professional atmosphere at which point representatives are supposed to communicate accompanying any of population, and have to introduce co a system in a group. QWL for academicians is an attitudinal reaction to the dominant work environment and supposed five work atmosphere rules that contain role stress, task traits, administrative, fundamental and creed oral traits to straightforwardly and obliquely shape academicians knowledge, attitudes and behaviour (ampson&Winter, 2016). Work-growth balance usually is pronounced expected completed when an individual's right to a fulfilled existence inside and outside the compensated work is established and esteemed. Some people grant permission apply it to the bendable occupied arrangements that admit two together persons and non-persons to avail of occupied arrangements that support a balance 'tween work blames and private responsibilities (Al-Mutairi &Marafi, 2012).It leads to the agreeable and whole unification of work, kin, social interactions and personal history and is the magnitude at which point things are equally complicated in, and evenly compensated accompanying their professional duty and their family part. Work-history balance, in allure fullest sense, can be described as an individual's level of vindication, engrossment or unity between the multiple functions in growth. One's best individual work-history balance will change over time, frequently on a regularly base. The right balance, for an individual contemporary will probably be various for later (Punia& Khosla, 2009).The second rule of status of work history is organization civilization and humidity. Miryala (2012) emphasize the need of adopting work life balance tactics for assistants education at various levels. Based upon the various elements particularly concerning administration and private organization teachers, the study projected a correct tactics for work existence balance. Since Quality of work history has direct correlates accompanying cost obtained on representatives either by inflow or efflux. When clerks.Stress and pressures, in addition to administrative change in academies have led to the raised significance of research knowledgeable the impact of seen job stress, work-growth balance and work-existence conflict among scholars yet, very few studies have checked lecturers' talent to balance work and individual growth, and overcome work-life conflict as believed by Bell, Rajendran & Theiler (2012).The next rule of feature of work history is relation and cooperation. Within the arrangement of beneficial influence pride has been labeled as a emotional idea that can show mental well-being, as in self-amount, the subject is acknowledged as bearing profit, with negative and helpful

facets. Other ideas have again been identified accompanying excellent pertinence, self-image, self-agreement and self-esteem (Chandra, S., & Varghese, 2019). According to Lee, Back, & Chan (2015), the idea of education happiness can be interpreted by inspiration and success of the lecturer, because of ability set (elasticity) and approaches (managing) that it expands to get to us the demands and professional troubles, thrashing ruling class and optimizing their own movement.The fourth rule of feature of work history is preparation and incident. Training and development isa administrative venture proposed at outdoing the performance of individual and groups. QWL authorizes the staff members at each ranking to energetically take part in building the arranging atmosphere by cultivating an administrative model to produce the organizational triumphs. (Nanjundeswaraswamy, & Swamy, 2013).The next rule of character of work growth is compensation and rewards. Even if the pace of our organization does not help the judgment/amount of the importance of happiness or individual accomplishment, we are heartened to plan our epoch-to- day to overcome the challenges of new existence, for instance, claim enrollment, financial balance, safeguard us from city intensity and take conduct that promote our tangible, passionate and friendly (Swamy, Nanjundeswaraswamy, &Rashmi, 2015). Compensation and rewards are motivational determinants, best choice performer is likely the rewards, and this builds contest with the agents to work hard and attain two together administrative and individual aims. Quality of occupied life is guide vindication accompanying earnings, working hours and active environments, expressing the "fundamental elements of a excellent of work history" as; dependable work surroundings, impartial wages, equal business event and moment for progress (Tabassum, 2012). High QW L would help to fulfil employee's needs, skilled by fulfil the the administrative aims efficiently and capably. Quality of work life is a vital multi-spatial build that involves concepts to a degree task safety, reward arrangements, preparation and career progresses space and partnership hesitation making (Mogaddam& Azad, 2015).The sixth domain of feature of work existence is conveniences. Facilities like fare duty, transportation, safety etc, play main duty in realization of the goals and goals by fulfilling two together the material and emotional needs of the attendants. Many employers have establish it in consideration of admit alternate work plans for their employees. This is individual habit to develop member productivity and self-esteem. The benefits of these alternate work plans widespread to the member include bendable work hours, smaller or no exchange, and a affluent working surroundings (Mogaddam, & Azad, 2015).The seven rule of value of work growth is task satisfaction and Job freedom. Job delight is the favourableness or un favourableness accompanying that employees view their work. Like inspiration, it is impressed for one atmosphere. Different facets of the job, to a degree pay, publicities, project, trimming benefits, one's co-traders support, and overdone occupied hours are guide levels of satisfaction (Ajala, 2013).Job delight is the favorableness or unfavourableness accompanying that laborers view their work. As accompanying motivation, it is stirred apiece surroundings. Job delight is impacted by task design. Jobs

that are rich in beneficial concerned with manner of behaving ingredients to a degree autonomy, difference, task correspondence, task meaning and response contribute to attendant's delight (Huzzard, Hellström, & Lifvergren, 2013). Likewise, introduction is main cause the employee's agreement apiece work group donates to vindication. If better performance leads to bigger rewards and if these rewards are visualized as fair and impartial, therefore results in upgraded satisfaction. On the other hand, incompetent rewards can bring about discontent. In either case, vindication becomes response that influences individual's self-concept and motivation to act. The total conduct-delight friendship is a constant system, making it troublesome to evaluate the impact of vindication on ambition or on performance, and weakness-versa. (edeurwaerdere and others., 2016).

D. Correlation between Measures

Professional commitment is a form of work commitment that is deliberate to influence depiction and other work consequences. delight, administrative assurance, intentions change, and administrative political independence nature.. Therefore, it is estimated that feature of work growth will likewise influence the professional commitment. (Hamidi, & Mohamadi, 2012).. Metacognitive knowledge is a mainstay of deliberate education that needs to be promoted and backed in the education declaration. Further, metacognitive awareness is an inclination essential for those coming the education field. In order to stage learning and accomplishment, lecturers must support scholars in the incident of metacognitive awareness, as it will help scholar to self-indicate and expand as existence-long learners (Gregory & Chapman, 2012). Therefore, metacognitive awareness is particularly inevitable knowledge for those pupils studying expected education experts (Baylor, & Ritchie, 2002). Professional assurance have revealed that staff members' obligation-connected performances towards their arrangement is closely connected to private traits to a degree age, gender, matrimonial rank and level of instruction to work-connected conditions aforementioned as task safety, proceeds level, career space, total age in the arrangement, age in the current position and cadre to task delight to feature of work-history, and perceived administrative support (Ortiz, Facchetti, & Marks 2010). A study by Lew and others., (2009) implies that the academic will present greater obligation to the instructional organization they are active for if they receive a good support apiece area in carrying out their aims. Taking care of the academic's well-being would expand an concerning feelings and intuition assurance between the staff to the skill (Daud and others, 2007). Recognition from the school in enjoying the academic gifts will encourage a exercise regime designed to increase heart and lung activity while toning muscles research result and the childbirth of far-reaching education quality. Interestingly, it is good to maintain those the one have extreme concerning feelings and intuition commitment than those the one have extreme duration assurance. Wasti (2005) have also concurred that bearing concerning feelings and intuition assurance would reduce the chance of the academic leaving. According to Murphy (2009) bearing a extreme need to deliver in the arranging would only means that the stick will only work

just to guarantee that they are still active in the arranging. Whereas, staffs that have high desire to deliver will present maximum offerings to the arranging. Metacognitive awareness maybe labeled as an main facet to improve the health of things (Shamstalab and others., 2014). It is trusted that improved metacognitive knowledge causes success a satisfied growth, and that health empowers things to use these abilities and in the end enhance their delight accompanying history (Georghiades, A., & Eiroa-Orosa, 2020). Commitment is the type of utilization that is to say whether one is a lasting stick or working on contract basis. The type of trade specifies main facts about the job freedom within institution cause a permanent stick has task safety inasmuch as contracted representatives do not. This meets expectations the prominence as a essential element that influences administrative assurance of members (Pekeren, & Başdaş, 2022). The connected literatures and studies provided most wanted information and culture for the subject substitute specifically on the connection with variables and by means of what these variables and their signs affect each one. The information gathered from renowned philosopher donated accompanying much understanding in the expression of the theoretical foundation and in the incident of the inquiry.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study engages the determinable non – exploratory design means of research using equating method. The plan and makeup concerning this research search out specify a believable answer to a research question. Its purpose search out express available traits in the way that realization, stances, action, and relationships. The non – exploratory all-inclusive system is appropriate for the hearing for it handles the professional obligation as a function of metacognitive awareness on characteristic of work history and allure connection. Variables are not maneuvered; they are only labeled and are intentional as they occur in a unrefined background (Educational Research, 2011). Descriptive survey is valuable in trying gospels on that controlled judgments can be based. It supplies essential information about the character of objects and guys and more plays a big contained the happening of the instruments for the calculations of entirety, agents that are operating fully types of determinable research as dossier gathering mechanism. The explanatory-correlational survey plan is appropriate for the case for it handles the writing and determination of two together free and weak variables (Creswell & Garrett, 2008). The verdicts of these were distinguishing to the framework of all elementary schools of Caraga, Davao Oriental. The chance for the overall relevance of the results are restricted for one outlook, and the sample, correspondingly, in spite of skilled could be coarse buildings, the verdicts concede possibility not have overall relevance to added structures. Presented in Figure 2 is the map of the Philippines emphasize the Province of Davao Oriental incorporating 17 domains at which point the city of Caraga Province of Davao Oriental is situated in Region XI. Moreover, bestowed in the figure was the vicinity plan of the accused at which point public basic schools of Tarragona is situated. The picked public simple schools of Caraga District, Davao Oriental was chosen as the research

background. The likelihood for the accepted relevance of the judgments were restricted apiece opportunity, and the sample, accordingly, in spite of skilled maybe universal countenance, the judgments grant permission not have general relevance to additional orders.

The venue of the study was located at Caraga, Davao Oriental. The respondents were 300 public elementary schools students in Caraga District coming from 20 public elementary schools. Furthermore, the place of the respondents and the conduct of study are located in the Municipality of Caraga, Davao Oriental, Philippines

The distribution of respondents was as follows:

School A: 50, School B: 27, School C: 13, School D: 32, School E: 19, School F: 21, School G: 29, School H: 19, School I: 27, School J: 29. Subject to a survey of a total of 300 respondents.

Moreover, the researcher considered the inclusion and exclusion criteria in the selection of the respondents of the study. The teacher respondents are regular teachers among public elementary schools in Manay Central District whose plantilla numbers are in the Department of Education. Teachers are willing to submit themselves and are permitted by their school heads to undergo the survey to be conducted. Those teachers who voluntarily agree with the informed consent are included in the survey, hence, teachers who clearly confessed their denial are excluded from the study. The study excluded all Junior High School, grade 11 and grade 12 students who are below 18 years of age. Further, the researcher considers teachers who decided to withdraw or back out during the actual administration of the survey questionnaires.

Three major research instruments are use in this study. The independent variable questionnaire was adapted from (Meyer, Allen & Smith, 1993) on professional commitment. The questionnaire measure by the respondents' views on professional commitment in terms of affective professional commitment (APC), continuance professional commitment (CPC), and normative professional commitment.

Prior to the conduct of actual survey, the researcher conducted a survey with a total of 50 respondents, for reliability. This questionnaire has a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.783 suggesting that the items have relatively high internal consistency.

Part 2 of The first part of the research instrument in this study was adapted questionnaire from the Modified Version of Metacognitive Awareness Inventory for Teachers (MAIT) developed by It encompasses the six factors of Metacognitive Awareness. The validated survey questionnaire annexed on this paper be seen in the appendices part. Items were clustered under six pre-determined domains, which are: declarative knowledge; procedural knowledge; conditional knowledge; planning; monitoring; and evaluating. This questionnaire has a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.792 suggesting that the items have relatively high internal consistency.

Part three of the research instrument in this study was adapted questionnaire from Mirkamali & Thani, (2011). It encompasses the nine factors of quality of work life. The validated survey questionnaire annexed on this paper be seen in the appendices part. This questionnaire has a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.853 suggesting that the items have relatively high internal consistency. Items were clustered under nine pre-determined domains, which are: work environment; organization culture and climate; relation and co-operation; training and development; compensation and rewards; facilities; job satisfaction and Job security; autonomy of work; and adequacy of resources.

The Likert Scale is use as basis in describing the level of the professional commitment. Likert Scale requires individuals to tick on the box/blank in response to a large number of items concerning an attitude, object, and stimulus. First, the researcher's adviser created a duly signed request letter to the Davao Eastern Directorate via her Gmail and Google Drive, allowing the researcher to conduct a survey among various public primary school teachers in Caraga South District. Department of Davao Oriental.

In addition, the researchers sent another letter to each school teacher in the Caraga South district asking them to conduct a survey. The researchers asked the principal of the school for permission to distribute the survey questionnaire to each teacher. After the application was approved, an investigation was conducted. Three school district teacher educators and one former teacher were surveyed and commented on its content and structure. For scheduling reasons, the survey was distributed simultaneously to her 303 teachers in her 13 schools in San Isidro. The teacher's email address was taken from her school's website. The schools selected are a representative sample of different levels of primary school. Each teacher received an email inviting them to participate. The survey was personalized by emailing each participant a link enabling them to participate in the survey. If teachers did not wish to participate, they were asked to reply to the email and provide their reasons for not participating, their age, gender, and total years of teaching experience. A teacher who did not respond or only partially completed the measure received her email reminder two weeks later. Of her 303 teachers contacted, 300 participated in the survey. Finally, researchers counted and tabulated all the data collected from the respondents for statistical analysis. Statistical results were analyzed and interpreted.

The following are the statistical tools that are employ by the researcher in the analysis and interpretation of the data:

Mean and Frequency. This is use to determine the level of professional commitment of teacher, metacognitive awareness and quality of work life in answer to sub-problems 1 and 2.

Pearson r. This is use to find out if there is a significant relationship between professional commitment of teacher, metacognitive awareness and quality of work life in answer to sub-problem 3.

Regression. This employ to determine the domain in the professional commitment of teacher and metacognitive awareness significantly predicts and quality of work life.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The presentation, analysis and interpretation of the acquired data are depicted in this part of the paper based on the research objectives of this study.

The flow of presentation on the stated topic is as follows: level of metacognitive awareness, level of quality of work life, and level of professional commitment, correlation between metacognitive awareness and professional commitment; correlation between quality of work life and professional commitment; and the extent of influence of predictor variables on professional commitment

Table 1 Level of Metacognitive Awareness

The first objective was to determine the level of metacognitive awareness of elementary school teachers through a survey questionnaire with the following indicators: declarative knowledge, procedural knowledge, conditional knowledge, planning, mentoring, and evaluating. Shown in Table 1 are the results for

metacognitive awareness. The computations yielded an overall mean of 4.36 or very high and a standard deviation of 0.33 and descriptive interpretation of very high. This means that metacognitive awareness is always manifested by the respondents. The results revealed that declarative knowledge has the highest mean score with the value of 4.46 which is described as very high. In contrast with the lowest indicator of procedural knowledge has obtained a lower mean score of 4.19 which described as high.

The very extreme level of metacognitive knowledge, as rated for one accused, signifies that declarative information is grasped dominant, as visualized in two together local and worldwide studies. The teachers acquire the inevitable knowledge, skills and approaches to act tasks under various conditions, they exhibit a extreme metacognitive knowledge (Mahdavi and others., 2014).

Therefore, these strategies are expected to increase awareness of his or her abilities and the excellent learning features that influence cognitive processing as they are compatible with the views of different authors. (Iwai, 2011; Mahdavi, 2014) who stated that teachers need to progress in providing structure, as well as the framework and evaluation. Furthermore, this domain in metacognitive awareness entails thinking about the future and trying to assume control over the future events by consolidating and managing resources so they can gratify to the successful completion of the set forth objectives.

Table 2: Metacognitive Awareness

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Declarative Knowledge	0.40	4.46	Very High
Procedural Knowledge	0.39	4.19	High
Conditional Knowledge	0.44	4.42	High
Planning	0.46	4.37	Very High
Monitoring	0.50	4.41	Very High
Evaluating	0.40	4.31	Very High
Overall	0.33	4.36	Very High

V. LEVEL OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE

Shown in Table 2 are the mean scores for the indicators of quality of work life with an overall mean of 4.16 described as high with a standard deviation of 0.24. The high level result indicated that quality of work life is oftentimes manifested. The cited overall mean score was the result gathered from the computed mean scores of its indicators. It could be gleaned from the data that the indicator with the highest mean rating of 4.20 or very high is – facilities. In contrast, indicator with the lowest mean rating of 3.90 or high is job satisfaction and job security.

The level of quality of work life is high, derived from the responses which are all at a high level, organization culture and climate; relation and co-operation;; compensation and rewards; job satisfaction and Job security; autonomy of work; adequacy of resources and work environment; training and development and facilities rated very high. This indicates that quality of work life of

teacher help motivating the environment, work in good conditions, and having for personal care.

In effect Ulusoy et al., (2011) added that teachers, who are responsible for creating a supportive environment that facilitates and increases students' learning, often provide this external support. The teachers' role in facilitating students' motivation is perceived through their support for developing students' autonomy, relevance, relatedness, competence, teachers' interests, and teachers' self-efficacy about teaching their subject. Though students' motivation to learn can be intrinsic or extrinsic, the role of the teacher in supporting their learning and creating the right environment will further enhance their motivation to learn.

This is in parallel with the results of the study of various authors (Santos&Taveira-Pinto 2013; Kumar et al., 2020) that Work environment is a place in which one works. It is a social and professional environment in which

employees are supposed to interact with a number of people, and have to work in coordination with one another. QWL for academicians is an attitudinal response to the prevailing work environment and posited five work environment domains that include role stress, job

characteristics, supervisory, structural and sectoral characteristics to directly and indirectly shape academic experiences, attitudes and behavior.

Table 2: Quality of Work life

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Work Environment	0.45	4.35	Very High
Organization Culture and Climate	0.37	4.02	High
Relation and co-operation	0.49	4.18	High
Training and Development	0.46	4.42	Very High
Compensation and Rewards	0.37	3.89	High
Facilities	0.45	4.44	Very High
Job Satisfaction and Job Security	0.34	3.83	High
Autonomy of Work	0.39	4.12	High
Adequacy of Resources	0.51	4.16	High
Overall	0.24	4.16	High

VI. LEVEL OF PROFESSIONAL COMMITMENT

Shown in Table 3 are the mean scores for the indicators of professional commitment with an overall mean of 4.36 described as very high with a standard deviation of 0.341. The very high level result indicated that professional commitment is always manifested. The cited overall mean score was the result gathered from the computed mean scores of its indicators. It could be gleaned from the data that the indicator with highest mean rating of 4.38 or very high is – normative professional commitment. In contrast, indicator with the lowest mean rating of 3.82 or high is affective professional commitment.

Result accompanied a very extreme level of professional assurance. This displays a able and dedicated school heads is individual of ultimate critical determinants in the happiness of some instruction system. A school

heads the one is really dedicated to their declaration is individual that puts graduates’ education and interests above entirety different (Gaan and others., 2008). This displays that school heads powerful affection to the assistants and to the declaration, have trustworthiness to wait that declaration for a rational magnitude, have the right choice of the declaration and have sense of faithfulness to the declaration. The result is parallel accompanying the inquiry attended by Delice, Aydin, & Kardeş (2009) as an educator is a professional essentially skilled is a accountability to the declaration to further the declaration what would include education sufficiently to likely advance the declaration and to offer support of associates just recording the declaration in order that through displaying act. This friendship of an teacher to professional associates and the declaration itself supports the blame to educate even better.

Table 3: Professional Commitment

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Affective Professional Commitment	0.48	4.35	Very High
Continuance Professional Commitment	0.46	4.37	Very High
Normative Professional Commitment	0.45	4.38	Very High
Overall	0.41	4.36	Very High

VII. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE QUALITYWORK LIFE AND PROFESSIONAL COMMITMENT

Presented in Table 4 are the results of the test of the significance on the relationship between the variables involved in the study. The overall r-value of

0.5331 with a p-value of $p < 0.01$ which was lesser than a 0.05 signified the null hypothesis was rejected. It meant that as the metacognitive awareness increase

there is also a corresponding increase on professional commitment. This showed that the overall teaching competence is significantly related to professional commitment.

All indicators of metacognitive awareness when correlated with overall professional commitment

Table 4: Significance of the Relationship between the Metacognitive Awareness and Professional Commitment

Metacognitive Awareness	Professional Commitment			
	Affective Professional Commitment	Continuance Professional Commitment	Normative Professional Commitment	Overall
Declarative Knowledge	.380* (0.000)	.363* (0.000)	.293* (0.000)	.392* (0.000)
Procedural Knowledge	.403* (0.000)	.364* (0.000)	.301* (0.000)	.405* (0.000)
Conditional Knowledge	.519* (0.000)	.466* (0.000)	.408* (0.000)	.528*(0.000)
Planning	.382* (0.000)	.382* (0.000)	.271* (0.000)	.393* (0.000)
Monitoring	.209* (0.000)	.247* (0.000)	.202* (0.000)	.249* (s0.000)
Evaluating	.485* (0.000)	.452* (0.000)	.407* (0.000)	.508* (0.000)
Overall	.509* (0.000)	.489* (0.000)	.404* (0.000)	.531* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

obtained r values of .392, .405, .528, .249, .508, and .531, respectively and $p < 0.01$ greater than the level of significance hence, significant.

There is a significant relationship between the two variables in which metacognitive awareness relatively influences professional commitment. It was mentioned in the study of Diaz et al., (2015) that teachers promote metacognition by first building awareness among learners that metacognition exists; thus, classes of competencies yield the most exceptional results and foster students learning.

Similarly, metacognition teachers make students more conscious of how to regulate how they think. This can be accomplished when teachers prepare, track, assess and change their instructional goals and teaching strategies according to the needs of their students and the sociocultural context (Belet & Güven (2011).

Moreover, scholars can speed metacognition by shaping their own thinking loudly and by building questions that prompt thoughtful thinking in pupils. Explicit command hindering one thinks through a task is owned by construction these abilities in pupils (Gregory & Chapman, 2012).

VIII. SIGNIFICANCE ON THE INFLUENCE OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE AND PROFESSIONAL COMMITMENT

Depicted in Table 5 is the result of the test of relationship between quality of work life is significantly related with professional commitment. This relationship was tested at 0.05 level of significance. In particular, it revealed a positive and significant relationship between all indicators of quality of work life and classroom professional commitment, as revealed in the p-value of less than 0.05, and with an overall r value of .667 and $p < 0.01$. When work environment is correlated with the indicators of professional commitment with the all of the R values where less than $p < 0.05$ significant level hence, significant, except, job satisfaction and job security and autonomy of work with an r value of .107 and .084 and $p = 0.064$ and $p = 0.145$.

When organization culture and climate is correlated with the indicators of professional commitment with the all of the R values where less than $p < 0.05$ significant level hence, significant.

Relation and co-operation is correlated with the indicators of professional commitment with the all of the R values where greater than $p < 0.05$ significant level hence, significant.

The present study reveals a significant relationship between quality of work life and professional commitment. This implies that quality of work life influences professional commitment which can be seen on the data. This confirms the study of Huang et al., (2007) the one pronounced that arrangements that offer better QWL have the advantage of win valuable trained workers. Having better QWL accompanying all of allure dimensions is

seemingly to present the members an feeling of appreciation, that will create bureaucracy enhance faithful and committed to the institution. These judgments support Also, Huang and others. (2007) submitted for managers that the different practices of QWL need expected linked together so that have high-quality results in the individuals' ability memory and assurance.

Table 5: Significance of the Relationship between the he Quality of Work life and Professional Commitment

Quality of Work life	Professional Commitment			
	Affective Professional Commitment	Continuance Professional Commitment	Normative Professional Commitment	Overall
Work Environment	.529* (0.000)	.584* (0.000)	.656* (0.000)	.666* (0.000)
Organization Culture and Climate	.270* (0.000)	.209* (0.000)	.259* (0.000)	.279* (0.000)
Relation and co-operation	.501* (0.000)	.533* (0.000)	.459* (0.000)	.564* (0.000)
Training and Development	.590* (0.000)	.603* (0.000)	.507* (0.000)	.643* (0.000)
Compensation and Rewards	.221* (0.000)	.310* (0.000)	.279* (0.000)	.305* (0.000)
Facilities	.517* (0.000)	.502* (0.000)	.417* (0.000)	.543* (0.000)
Job Satisfaction and Job Security	.128* (0.026)	.161* (0.005)	-.009 (0.881)	.107 (0.064)
Autonomy of Work	-.052 (0.372)	-.073 (0.207)	-.099 (0.088)	-.084 (0.145)
Adequacy of Resources	.209* (0.000)	.188* (0.001)	.266* (0.000)	.249* (0.000)
Overall	.592* (0.000)	.611* (0.000)	.562* (0.000)	.667* (0.000)

IX. THE EXTENT OF INFLUENCE OF PREDICTOR VARIABLES ON PROFESSIONAL COMMITMENT

Data shown in Table 6 is the regression coefficients to test Data shown in Table 6 is the regression coefficients to test the significant influence of the overall metacognitive awareness on quality of work life on. Using the Regression Analysis, the data revealed that the influence of metacognitive awareness on quality of work life on professional commitment has $p < 0.05$. This means that metacognitive awareness on quality of work life influences professional commitment since the probability value is $p < 0.05$. The R2 value of 0.511 implies that 51.1 percent of the

metacognitive awareness on quality of work life can be attributed to the variance of professional commitment while the remaining 48.9 percent were attributed to other factors not covered by the study. However, quality of work life, emerged as a significant predictor of professional commitment, with p values of $p < 0.05$ and beta-coefficients of .536.

Table 6: The extent of Influence of Predictor Variables on Professional Commitment

Professional Commitment (Dependent Variables)				
Independent Variables	β (Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	t	Sig.
Constant	-.938	.301	-3.113	.002
Metacognitive Awareness (MA)	.290	.360	6.381	.000
Quality of Work Life (QWL)	.536	.898	11.809	.000
R	.715			
R²	.511			
F	155.34			
p	.000			

X. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions, a number of recommendations are offered. Since there is a very high level of metacognitive awareness, it is recommended for them to have subjects focused on enhancing the metacognitive awareness of their soon-to-be teachers. Since if metacognitive awareness is harnessed on the undergraduate years of these aspiring teachers, being proactive with initiating how to go about the strategies in teaching will be natural to them. In addition, school heads have consistent, career-long effective and applicable learning opportunities to enhance teaching skills, in which each teacher can gain and develop the skills they need. The significant relationship recommended that the policymakers, particularly the officials from the Department of Education, review and revisit their existing educational policies if it addresses the demands and challenges of being a 21st-century educator, mainly focusing on how to heighten teachers' metacognition, hence, also improving their teachers commitment.

Finally, future studies toward examining other variables that can possibly influence between metacognitive awareness which will be of utmost importance to the research community shall be taken into consideration.

Quality of work life, on the other hand, is urged that it is essential to be more effective and active there by accomplish task satisfaction that consecutively guarantees favorable molding of junior society. Simultaneously work life balance too helps the faculty expected more creative in their job skills with their individual obligations and family proceedings.

In the present study, researcher had explored the various factors that have been found significantly affecting the status of work life balance. Lastly, this research study can be a springboard for similar studies in a different context.

XI. CONCLUSION

Conclusions are drawn from the findings of the study, and the results showed that metacognitive awareness among teachers is very high in all six domains, especially in declarative knowledge. Consequently, the domains of teacher competence also displayed results of very high in all domains, but the curriculum got the highest mean. These factors help them develop metacognition, because it refers to the mechanisms that enable people to reflect on their own cognitive abilities since it is parallel with the study of Diaz et al., (2015) asserting that metacognition is an important concept in the professional development of teachers, because if a teacher wants his students to think metacognitively, he himself should be advanced metacognitive.

Consequently, the level of quality of work life is rated high in terms of organization culture and climate; relation and co-operation; compensation and rewards; job satisfaction and Job security; autonomy of work; and adequacy of resources except, work environment; training and development and facilities were rated very high.

The level of professional commitment of teachers is rated very high.

The metacognitive awareness of school heads significantly influences professional commitment. The study thus support the proposition of Adaryani, Jalili and Roshani (2013) pronounced that metacognitive knowledge causes success a happy history, what welfare empowers things to use these abilities and in the end enhance their delight accompanying existence. The kind of work history considerably influences professional commitment. The study accordingly supports the proposition of Huang and others. (2007) submitted for managers that the various practices of QWL need expected linked together so that have the best results in the things' ability memory and obligation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The exodus of this project is never an isolated endeavour. The researcher would like to express her profound heartfelt gratitude to the family and friends who gave extended their help to finish this study. Sincere thanks due to the following:

Dr. Eugenio S. Guhao, Jr., the Dean of the Professional Schools, the research adviser, for giving his time and effort the in helping the researcher to finish this study and share his expertise in the field of research;

To my adviser, Dr. Lorna T. General, for giving answers to her questions and patiently checking her manuscript;

To the Panel of examiners, Dr. Reynante L. Genuba, Dr. Mary Ann D. Tarusan, Dr. Elleinne Rose Olive and Dr. Jocelyn C. Bacasmot, for their constructive criticisms that paved the way for the completion of the study;

Miss Sarra, for her precious time and for meticulously carrying out corrections meant in improving the manuscript;

Dr. Mary Ann C. Sobrecarey, Schools District Supervisor of the Division of Caraga Davao Oriental, for allowing the researcher to conduct of the study;

The researcher's fellow administrators and teachers whose beliefs extended to the researcher to finish her studies;

Lastly, her loving family, for making the researcher's first steps toward the future of varied glances this journey is deeply dedicated, her sisters, for understanding the pressure to succeed, her husband Garry Salvador Ongcay for the consideration of most times with this study.

And above all, to the almighty God, who made everything possible and forgiving her guidance, peace of mind, wisdom and strength to pursue the graduate course even in the midst of trials. It is Him, who let all things work together and bestowed all the gifts she needed towards the success of her endeavor and reached its highest peak.

To all, thank you very much

ABOUT THE AUTHOR(S)

- Lynlyn Lanos Ongcay is a Public School Teacher. She is a candidate for the degree of Master of Arts in Education major in Educational Management at the University of Mindanao Davao City, Philippines.
- Dr. Lorna T. General is a faculty under the program of educational management of the University of Mindanao Professional Schools of University of Mindanao Davao City, Philippines.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Adaryani, M. M., Jalili, S., & Roshani, K. (2013). A study of meta-cognitive strategies, spiritual health and life satisfaction in college students. *Journal of Life Science and Biomedicine*, 3(5), 367-370.
- [2.] Agrawal, S., & Goyal, N. (2012, June). Analysis of thompson sampling for the multi-armed bandit problem. In *Conference on learning theory* (pp. 39-1). *JMLR Workshop and Conference Proceedings*.
- [3.] Ajala, E. M. (2013). Quality of work life and workers wellbeing: The industrial social workers approach. *IFE Psychologia: An International Journal*, 21(2), 46-56.
- [4.] Al-Mutairi, A., & Marafi, A. (2012). Effect of the operating pressure on residual oil hydroprocessing. *Energy & fuels*, 26(12), 7257-7262.
- [5.] Baylor, A. L., & Ritchie, D. (2002). What factors facilitate teacher skill, teacher morale, and perceived student learning in technology-using classrooms?. *Computers & education*, 39(4), 395-414
- [6.] School Teacher Trainees. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 11(1), 51-57.
- [7.] Boas, A. A. V., & Morin, E. M. (2019). Emotional intelligence and quality of working life at federal institutions of higher education in Brazil. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(2), 255-274.
- [8.] Bell, A. S., Rajendran, D., & Theiler, S. (2012). Job stress, wellbeing, work-[life balance and work-life conflict among Australian academics. *E-journal of Applied Psychology*, 8(1).
- [9.] Boehman, J. (2006). *Affective, continuance, and normative commitment among student affairs professionals*. North Carolina State University.
- [10.] Chan, K. W., & Wyatt, T. A. (2007). Quality of work life: A study of employees in Shanghai, China. *Asia Pacific Business Review*, 13(4), 501-517.
- [11.] Chandra, S., & Varghese, D. T. (2019). Work environment in educational institutions: Work stress leads to work-life imbalance to academicians. *Asian Journal of Management Sciences & Education*, 8(2), 64-73.
- [12.] Conley, S., & You, S. (2009). Teacher role stress, satisfaction, commitment, and intentions to leave: A structural model. *Psychological reports*, 105(3), 771-786.
- [13.] Creswell, J. W., & Garrett, A. L. (2008). The "movement" of mixed methods research and the role of educators. *South African journal of education*, 28(3), 321-333.
- [14.] Daud, S. A., Yusen, R. D., Meyers, B. F., Chakinala, M. M., Walter, M. J., Aloush, A. A., ... & Hachem, R. R. (2007). Impact of immediate primary lung allograft dysfunction on bronchiolitis obliterans syndrome. *American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine*, 175(5), 507-513.
- [15.] Dedeurwaerdere, T., Admiraal, J., Beringer, A., Bonaiuto, F., Cicero, L., Fernandez-Wulff, P., ... & Vivero, J. L. (2016). Combining internal and external motivations in multi-actor governance

- arrangements for biodiversity and ecosystem services. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 58, 1-10.
- [16.] Delice, A., AYDIN, E., &Kardeş, D. (2009). Öğretmenadayıgözylematematikderskitaplarındagörselöğellerinkullanımı the use of visual objects in mathematics textbooks from the perspective of teacher candidate. *İstanbul TicaretÜniversitesi Fen BilimleriDergisi*, 8(16), 75-92.
- [17.] Delima, V. T. (2015). Professional identity, professional commitment and teachers' performance. *International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning*, 2(4), 1-12.
- [18.] Díaz, S., Demissew, S., Carabias, J., Joly, C., Lonsdale, M., Ash, N., ... &Zlatanova, D. (2015). The IPBES Conceptual Framework—connecting nature and people. *Current opinion in environmental sustainability*, 14, 1-16.
- [19.] Farooq, M., Hussain, M., Wahid, A., & Siddique, K. H. M. (2012). Drought stress in plants: an overview. *Plant responses to drought stress: From morphological to molecular features*, 1-33.
- [20.] Flavell, J. H. (1986). The development of children's knowledge about the appearance–reality distinction. *American Psychologist*, 41(4), 418.
- [21.] Gaan, S., Sun, G., Hutches, K., & Engelhard, M. H. (2008). Effect of nitrogen additives on flame retardant action of tributyl phosphate: phosphorus–nitrogen synergism. *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 93(1), 99-108.
- [22.] Georghiades, A., &Eiroa-Orosa, F. J. (2020). A randomised enquiry on the interaction between Wellbeing and Citizenship. *Journal of happiness studies*, 21(6), 2115-2139.
- [23.] Gopinath, R. (2020). Impact of Academic Leaders' Self-Actualization on Organisational Commitment in Tamil Nadu Universities–Through Structural Equation Modelling. *Test engineering and management*, 83, 24898-24904.
- [24.] Gregory, G. H., & Chapman, C. (2012). *Differentiated Instructional strategies: One size doesn't fit all*. Corwin press.
- [25.] Hamidi, F., &Mohamadi, B. (2012). Teachers' quality of work life in secondary schools. *International Journal of Vocational and Technical Education*, 4(1), 1-5.
- [26.] Huang, J., Li, Q., Sun, D., Lu, Y., Su, Y., Yang, X., ... & Chen, C. (2007). Biosynthesis of silver and gold nanoparticles by novel sundried *Cinnamomum camphora* leaf. *Nanotechnology*, 18(10), 105104.
- [27.] Huzzard, T., Hellström, A., &Lifvergren, S. (2013). Sensegiving across professional borders: readiness for system-wide change in cancer care. In *Proceedings to the EGOS Colloquium*.
- [28.] Ibrahim, M., Cao, C. G., Zhan, M., Li, C. F., & Iqbal, J. (2015). Changes of CO₂ emission and labile organic carbon as influenced by rice straw and different water regimes. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 12, 263-274.
- [29.] Iwai, Y. (2011). The effects of metacognitive reading strategies: Pedagogical implications for EFL/ESL teachers. *Reading*, 11(2), 150-159.
- [30.] Karim, F., & Rehman, O. (2012). Impact of job satisfaction, perceived organizational justice and employee empowerment on organizational commitment in semi-government organizations of Pakistan. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 3(4), 92.
- [31.] Kasim, A. A. M., &Darus, N. A. (2020). Metacognitive awareness level and strategy use in academic reading among ESL undergraduates. *Social Science Learning Education Journal*, 5(06), 180-186.
- [32.] Kohli, K., Ali, J., Ansari, M. J., &Raheman, Z. (2005). Curcumin: a natural antiinflammatory agent. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*, 37(3), 141.
- [33.] Kumar, Y., Tiwari, K. N., Singh, T., Sain, N. K., Laxmi, S., Verma, R. A. M. E. S. H., ... &Raliya, R. A. M. E. S. H. (2020). Nanofertilizers for enhancing nutrient use efficiency, crop productivity and economic returns in winter season crops of Rajasthan. *Annals of Plant and Soil Research*, 22(4), 324-335.
- [34.] Lane, K. A., Esser, J., Holte, B., & McCusker, M. A. (2010). A study of nurse faculty job satisfaction in community colleges in Florida. *Teaching and Learning in Nursing*, 5(1), 16-26.
- [35.] Lee, J. S., Back, K. J., & Chan, E. S. (2015). Quality of work life and job satisfaction among frontline hotel employees: A self-determination and need satisfaction theory approach. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*.
- [36.] Lew, H. L., Otis, J. D., Tun, C., Kerns, R. D., Clark, M. E., & Cifu, D. X. (2009). Prevalence of chronic pain, posttraumatic stress disorder, and persistent postconcussive symptoms in OIF/OEF veterans: polytrauma clinical triad. *J Rehabil Res Dev*, 46(6), 697-702.
- [37.] Locatelli, S., &Arroio, A. (2016). Contributions and limitations of a metavisual strategy from the perspective of students. In *Electronic proceedings of the ESERA 2015 Conference. Science education research: engaging learners for a sustainable future, part (Vol. 3, No. 3, pp. 437-442)*.
- [38.] Mahdavi, S. A., Jafari, S. M., Ghorbani, M., &Assadpoor, E. (2014). Spray-drying microencapsulation of anthocyanins by natural biopolymers: A review. *Drying technology*, 32(5), 509-518.
- [39.] Martínez, M. E., Baron, J. A., Lieberman, D. A., Schatzkin, A., Lanza, E., Winawer, S. J., ... & Greenberg, E. R. (2009). A pooled analysis of advanced colorectal neoplasia diagnoses after colonoscopic polypectomy. *Gastroenterology*, 136(3), 832-841
- [40.] McCready, L. T., & Soloway, G. B. (2010). Teachers' perceptions of challenging student behaviours in model inner city schools. *Emotional and Behavioural Difficulties*, 15(2), 111-123..

- [41.] Medland, N. A., McMahon, J. H., Chow, E. P., Elliott, J. H., Hoy, J. F., & Fairley, C. K. (2015). The HIV care cascade: a systematic review of data sources, methodology and comparability. *Journal of the International AIDS Society*, 18(1), 20634.
- [42.] Meyer, J. P., Allen, N. J., & Smith, C. A. (1993). Commitment to organizations and occupations: Extension and test of a three-component conceptualization. *Journal of applied psychology*, 78(4), 538.
- [43.] Miryala, R. K. (2012). and NagapriyaChiluka "Work-life balance amongst teachers" the IUP *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, VOL.
- [44.] Mirkamali, S. M., & Thani, F. N. (2011). A study on the quality of work life (QWL) among faculty members of University of Tehran (UT) and Sharif University of Technology (SUT). *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 29, 179-187.
- [45.] Mogaddam, A., & Azad, N. (2015). An empirical investigation on factors influencing on quality of work life. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 3(4), 375-380.
- [46.] Mukherjee, U. (2010). *Postcolonial environments: Nature, culture and the contemporary Indian novel in English*. Springer.
- [47.] Murphy, M. P. (2009). How mitochondria produce reactive oxygen species. *Biochemical journal*, 417(1), 1-13.
- [48.] Nanjundeswaraswamy, T. S., & Swamy, D. R. (2013). Review of literature on quality of worklife. *International journal for quality research*, 7(2), 201-214.
- [49.] Ortiz, R. P., Facchetti, A., & Marks, T. J. (2010). High-k organic, inorganic, and hybrid dielectrics for low-voltage organic field-effect transistors. *Chemical reviews*, 110(1), 205-239.
- [50.] Pekerem, M., & Başdaş, Ö. (2022). Professional Commitment and Work Life Quality Levels of Nurses. *Ordu Üniversitesi Hemşirelik Çalışmaları Dergisi*, 5(1), 32-40.
- [51.] Punia, V., & Kamboj, M. (2013). Quality of work-life balance among teachers in higher education institutions. *Learning Community-An International Journal of Educational and Social Development*, 4(3), 197-208.
- [52.] Punia, B. K., & Khosla, M. (2009). Relational Analysis of Organisational Role Stress and Conflict Management Strategies in Indian Service Sector. *The Journal of Innovations*, 4(2), 87-96.
- [53.] Sampson, R. J., & Winter, A. S. (2016). The racial ecology of lead poisoning: Toxic inequality in Chicago neighborhoods, 1995-2013. *Du Bois Review: Social Science Research on Race*, 13(2), 261-283.
- [54.] Santos, C., & Taveira-Pinto, F. (2013). Analysis of different criteria to size rainwater storage tanks using detailed methods. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 71, 1-6.
- [55.] Shamstalab, R., Akbari, B., & Mosavi, S. (2014). The comparison of burnout, psychological well-being and meta-cognitive beliefs in teachers of normal and exceptional schools. *Kuwait Chapter of the Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 3(6), 91.
- [56.] Shoaib, H., & Khalid, M. I. (2017). Professional commitment of teacher educators: Future of nation builders. *Pakistan Vision*, 18(2), 163-178.
- [57.] Skalli, A., Theodossiou, I., & Vasileiou, E. (2008). Jobs as Lancaster goods: Facets of job satisfaction and overall job satisfaction. *The Journal of Socio-Economics*, 37(5), 1906-1920.
- [58.] Swamy, D. R., Nanjundeswaraswamy, T. S., & Rashmi, S. (2015). Quality of work life: scale development and validation. *International Journal of Caring Sciences*, 8(2), 281.
- [59.] Swann, G. P. (2010). The economics of standardization: An update. Report for the UK Department of Business, Innovation and Skills (BIS).
- [60.] Tabassum, A. (2012). Interrelations between quality of work life dimensions and faculty member job satisfaction in the Private Universities of Bangladesh. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 4(2), 78-89.
- [61.] Wang, J., Hernandez, Y., Lotya, M., Coleman, J. N., & Blau, W. J. (2009). Broadband nonlinear optical response of graphene dispersions. *Advanced Materials*, 21(23), 2430-2435.
- [62.] Wasti, S. A. (2005). Commitment profiles: Combinations of organizational commitment forms and job outcomes. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 67(2), 290-308.
- [63.] Ugurlu, H., & Ozutku, F. (2014). An evaluation on the use of social media in Turkey. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 147, 453-457.
- [64.] Ulusoy, H., Sarica, N., Arslan, S., Olcay, C., & Erkorkmaz, U. (2011). The efficacy of supervised physiotherapy for the treatment of adhesive capsulitis. *Bratislavské lekárskelisty*, 112(4), 204-207.
- [65.] Usmani, S. (2016). Perceived internal employability and leader member exchange as a way to reduce intention to quit via commitment. *Humanities and Social Sciences Review*, 5(2), 17-32.
- [66.] Williams, J. P., & Atkins, J. G. (2009). The role of metacognition in teaching reading comprehension to primary students. In *Handbook of metacognition in education* (pp. 26-43). Routledge.
- [67.] Yesilyurt, E. (2013). An analysis of teacher candidates' usage level of metacognitive learning strategies: Sample of a university in Turkey. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 8(6), 218.
- [68.] Yildiz, H., & Akdag, M. (2017). The Effect of Metacognitive Strategies on Prospective Teachers' Metacognitive Awareness and Self Efficacy Belief. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 5(12), 30-40.